

EVALUATION OF BARIUM PEROXIDE IN PRESENCE OF BARIUM SULPHIDE

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A method of estimating BaS and BaO₂ in a mixture of the two has been given. The process consists in the addition of CdCl₂ to the mixture when CdS and CdO₂ are formed. A part of this mixture is kept at 100° when CdO₂ is decomposed leaving CdS alone which is estimated. For estimation of peroxide it is treated with CH₃COOH and H₂O₂ liberated is estimated

In an attempt at preparing barium peroxide from barytes (Bradley and Jacob, B. P. 26060, 1898), a mixture, composing mostly of barium peroxide and the sulphide, was obtained. No analytical process is known for evaluating the peroxide content in a mixture like this. The well known permanganate method fails in this case owing to simultaneous generation of sulphuretted hydrogen and hydrogen peroxide. The present paper describes a process for estimating the percentage of barium peroxide in presence of the sulphide.

The process consists in treating the compounds with a solution of cadmium chloride which yields quantitatively a mixture of cadmium peroxide and the sulphide. The peroxide of cadmium is unstable at elevated temperatures and as such if a measure of the sulphide content alone is wanted the resulting mixture needs boiling for 10 to 15 minutes. This causes complete decomposition of the peroxide and the residual sulphide may then be estimated. For estimating the peroxide content, or both, the solution needs treatment with dilute acetic acid, which yields an equivalent amount of hydrogen peroxide leaving the cadmium sulphide intact. The insoluble cadmium sulphide can easily be separated from the peroxide solution and each may be estimated separately. The process was standardised against artificial mixtures of Merck's pure barium sulphide and barium peroxide. The table following will show the results obtained by the adoption of the present method. Although different weights of the artificial mixtures of the two components were taken for analysis, in each case the calculation of the percentage of each component was made ignoring the proportion of the remaining component.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Barium peroxide and barium sulphide were separately weighed and taken in a dry Erlenmeyer flask. This was then covered with previously cooled saturated solution of cadmium chloride (50 c.c. or more). The contents of the flask were well shaken and kept at a temperature not exceeding 5—8°. The resulting mixture was then acidified with dilute acetic acid in the cold and filtered quantitatively. For washing the precipitated cadmium sulphide, cold dilute acetic acid should be used. The filtrate was mixed with cold dilute sulphuric acid and titrated with standard potassium permanganate solution. The volume in c.c. of normal potassium permanganate required, multiplied by 0.084685 gives the weight of barium peroxide.

The residue left on the filter was transferred quantitatively in an evolution flask (capacity 200 c.c.), provided with a ground glass joint to which was attached a stoppered funnel (20 c.c. capacity). The stem of the funnel extended nearly to the bottom of the distilling flask ending in capillary. The side tube of the flask was connected to a system of four Erlenmeyer flasks, the first three containing standard iodine solution while the last one contained standard sodium thiosulphate solution. It was found necessary to maintain a constant flow of air through the entire system by means of a water-jet pump, connected to the exit end of the last wash bottle. This facilitated complete removal of the evolved sulphuretted hydrogen from the flask. For starting the experiment, pure concentrated hydrochloric acid should be

taken in the separating funnel and then the water-jet pump is to be started. The decomposition is promoted by warming slowly over a small flame. On cooling the contents of the wash bottles were mixed together and the excess of iodine titrated back with standard thiosulphate solution.

For estimating the percentage of barium sulphide alone the following procedure was adopted. The mixture was taken directly into the evolution flask and was treated with cadmium chloride solution. This gave immediately a precipitate of cadmium sulphide. The mixture was well shaken and then boiled for 10 to 15 minutes to decompose the unstable peroxide of cadmium. After this the sulphide was decomposed in the usual way and the liberated sulphuretted hydrogen absorbed in iodine.

It may be pointed out that the usual precautions for iodimetric method of estimating sulphides must be taken. The strength of iodine solution should preferably be maintained between $N/100$ and $N/10$. With more concentrated solution, the precipitated sulphur encloses a portion of the iodine, and this escapes subsequent titration with standard sodium thiosulphate solution. Results are given in the following tables :

TABLE I

Estimation of barium sulphide alone in a mixture of BaS and BaO₂

BaS (obs.) in %	...	91'507	91'510	91'510	91'506	91'505
BaS (calc.) in %	...	91'516	91'516	91'516	91'516	91'516

TABLE II

Estimation of barium peroxide and barium sulphide in a mixture

Substance.	Wt. taken.	% Calc.*	% Obs.
BaO ₂	0'1439 g.	76'61	76'59
BaS	0'1300	91'516	91'52
BaO ₂	0'1561	76'61	76'58
BaS	0'1124	91'516	91'53
BaO ₂	0'2579	76'61	76'63
BaS	0'1237	91'516	91'60
BaO ₂	0'3256	76'61	76'62
BaS	0'2147	91'516	91'52
BaO ₂	0'3509	76'61	76'62
BaS	0'2091	91'516	91'60

* The figure was calculated on the assumption that the other ingredient was absent.